

Factors Affecting Technology Transfer in the Security Industry, Vietnam

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Abstract:

The article presents the current status of technology transfer activities in the security industry in Vietnam, analyzes the form content, the current situation and the factors affecting technology transfer activities in the security sector. security in Vietnam. From there, the author conducted the evaluation of technology transfer results in the field of security industry in Vietnam.

Keywords: Technology transfer, security industry, Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Currently, the political - military situation in the world has many major changes, fundamental and rapid changes, in which the multi-polar world order is increasingly clearly shown and the emerging role of many countries. (Le The Mau, 2015). Terrorism raged in many places, armed conflicts took place in many countries, causing more and more migrants from the countries of Siria and Lebanon to the West, causing chaos in the face of society. Political crises lead to social and economic crises. The disagreement within the bloc as the EU is increasing, affecting not only countries in the region but also other countries in the world. Security policies of many countries, especially large countries, are adjusted. Right from the beginning of 2015, the US announced the National Security Strategy 2015; China announced the National Defense White Paper demonstrating the Military Strategy (May 2015); Russia announced the revised Maritime Doctrine (July 2015) and Japan passed the new National Security Bill, etc. (Le The Mau, 2015). That has caused many other countries, especially their interactive partners, to also make appropriate adjustments. This is also one of the reasons why the situation and competition among countries in each region and the global scope in 2015 have complicated and very drastic changes (Le The Mau, 2015). The problems of the South China Sea are also heating up when China's moves become more and more paradoxical when it comes to building a military airport and a military port on Gac Ma island, in the Paracel Islands of Vietnam.

The complicated developments mentioned above have made major countries, as well as many related countries, put themselves in a state of high vigilance. Modern military and security equipment is becoming more imperative than ever. This urgent requirement forces countries to increase the import of technology from abroad to ensure national security (including national security and domestic security).

The development of the internet has made the world flatter and flatter, shortening the geographical distance between countries. This also facilitates the development of high-tech criminals (especially hackers) and difficult to control. Hostile forces and criminals in many fields take full advantage of the development of information technology and postal and telecommunications services in intelligence, espionage, reactionary and terrorism activities. , vandalism ... and other criminal activities with increasingly sophisticated, cunning, and diversified operation tricks, especially the media, communication means, to deal with professional measures. of security agencies. The threats from these types of crimes are increasingly diverse and broader, not only for individuals and organizations, but also for national security agencies. Crime is not just individuals, but organizations, not only at NGOs, but in many cases, security representatives in countries. Typically, the LAN incident of the US Department of Defense was attacked by foreign intelligence. On the contrary, the US intelligence agency has also caused a lot of scandal when eavesdropping on the phones of millions of people around the world, including heads of states, including allied countries. intelligence gathering. Damage from these threats is not only property, health and life of individuals, but also can damage the security and property of the country; and not only confined within a country, but also in a cross-border perspective. These challenges force countries to have access to advanced, modern technologies to protect the assets of their own countries and their citizens. Importing technology from abroad will allow countries to meet urgent requirements for modern security equipment, shortening the time to research new technologies.

In recent years, science and technology have developed strongly, especially information technology, developed countries have been thoroughly applying new technologies to develop security industries, while improving efficiency. confidentiality, while minimizing the possibility of foreign technical intelligence agencies stealing intelligence through secret code activities. In addition to information technology, other fields of science, technology and technology have also developed strongly in recent years such as: biotechnology, nanotechnology, new material technology, which has brought about Great effect in the development of knowledge economy. Such strong development, on the one hand, requires countries to have strategies to access and absorb new technologies, increase national technological capacity, as well as increase national competitiveness. effectively protect national security, territorial sovereignty, security and safety of people's life. The change in technology in the world is happening quite quickly, therefore, access to new technology also needs to be done regularly and continuously to avoid too far behind other countries. This requirement also leads to a need for technology transfer, especially in the security industry.

The security requirements of economic entities are increasingly larger when the risks occur more frequently and unpredictably and are more difficult to overcome. According to the development of technology and the economy, this need becomes even more urgent. However, the backwardness of security products and services, especially provided by the state, makes the conflict between supply and demand elevated. In the security industry market will appear the phenomenon of scarcity of products and services, which can facilitate underground transactions, ignorance that the state does not control. Ensuring supply keeps up with demand leads to an increase in the need to adopt modern security technology overseas.

2. Forms, channels and objects of technology transfer in the field of security industry

2.1. Form of technology transfer

Technology in the security industry can be transferred vertically and horizontally.

Vertical technology transfer refers to technology transferred from research to production development. Therefore, it follows the evolutionary stage of invention, innovation and development, with this technology becoming more commercialized as it progresses through each stage. Vertical transfers can be within an institution or a transaction between, say, a research institute and a manufacturing company (UNIDO, 2002). Vertical technology transfer can carry out technology transfer that is not yet in the market (i.e. technology is still under the control of researcher and has not been implemented, the receiver can obtain completely new technology if implemented successfully), or technology already in the market (has been put into production and disseminated in the market) (Technology Management Department, 2013). Technologies in the civil security industry can be cooperatively transferred in this form in order to save research costs, as well as accelerate technology to market, reduce the intangible wear and tear of the public. technology and technology products in the context of today's rapidly changing technology.

Horizontal technology transfer refers to a technology already in the market transferred from one operating environment to another. This technology has been commercialized and the purpose is to popularize the technology and extend its application into other contexts. This form of transfer is used by companies wishing to maximize profits from their technology, but is unable to do this by selling the final product directly in a marketplace. . Horizontal technology transfer is more common when technology is transferred from industrialized countries to developing countries. Usually transfer in this form with no further improvement or change in technology, unless it needs to be modified to suit local circumstances or environmental regulations, in which there is a case when it is applied. Applying and / or refining will require a combination of vertical and horizontal technology transfer (UNIDO, 2002). Developing and underdeveloped countries often import technologies horizontally due to limited technological research capacity as well as limited investment capital for technology research and development. Ensuring security and safety in the country is largely dependent on technology and technology products transferred from abroad.

2.2. Channel and technology transfer object

* Channel of technology transfer:

According to the analysis of the Department of Technology Management, (2013), international technology transfer can be done in two channels: direct channel and indirect channel. For security industrial products, delivery is also possible through these two channels.

+ Live channels, including:

- Through transnational companies;
- Through the purchase of technology licenses;
- Through consulting companies on technology and technology transfer;
- Through foreign experts working in the locality, or technical staff internships, foreign students studying in developed countries return

These connections create the opportunity for the buyer to reach the true owners of the technology, so the chance of success is higher.

+ Indirect channels, including:

- Through local agents selling machines and equipment;
- Through international conferences and seminars'
- Through trade fairs and exhibitions;
- Through publications (advertising in newspapers, magazines, professional books);

These linkages are often difficult to create opportunities for recipients to have direct contact with the true owner of technology (Technology Management Department, 2013). For developing countries, often the import of technologies is usually indirect and often through third parties, limited access to source technologies due to insufficient qualifications and funding. to receive transferred new technology.

* Subjects of technology transfer

Subjects of technology transfer in the security industry are like other industrial sectors, including: (i) technical know-how (technological know-how); (ii) technological options and processes; solutions, specifications, drawings, technical diagrams; formulas, computer software, data information; (iii) solutions to rationalize production, innovate technology; (iv) machinery and equipment accompanying one of the above.

In many cases, because the owner countries often want to keep technical know-how, the majority of technology transfer objects in the security industry are often the transfer of products, machinery and equipment, rarely. technical know-how.

Technology products transferred under technology transfer projects in the security industry are quite diverse due to the needs of ensuring security and safety in society, including the military and civil sectors. Estimates are high. Technology products imported under technology transfer projects in the military field often focus on tools, specialized vehicles, and professional technical equipment serving combat operations of forces. the amount of weapons and security, such as weapons and tools for suppression and crime prevention; audiovisual, surveillance, inspection, forensic equipment and other professional documents; specialized equipment for terrorism and riot prevention; specialized means of transport serving transportation, patrol, search and rescue and rescue activities; security and safety equipment in the military and other civilian.

In the field of civil security, in some countries, weapons and weapons for individuals are strictly controlled to ensure the goal of ensuring domestic security. Therefore, products and vehicles transferred often include equipment such as fire protection, anti-theft cameras, low-damage weapons for self-defense purposes. These products can be imported directly to the market by private enterprises.

3. Factors affecting technology transfer in the security industry

3.1. Theoretical basis of factors affecting technology transfer

There are many studies on factors influencing technology transfer in many different fields.

Zhao and Reisman (1992) argue that technology transfer is a very complex process and requires interaction between organizations. Spann et al. (1995) have shown that although there are many studies on integrated methods or models for measuring the processes, implementation and impact of international technology transfer (ITT). However, the results often lack standardization and consistency. Differences in attitudes, goals, and roles can contribute to the measurement of progress, ultimate success, and overall results in technology transfer (Lai, 2011, p. 1219).

Kumaraswamy and Shrestha (2002) point out that the properties of the assignor and the transferee are essential to the success of ITT. Malik (2002) argues that the successful achievement of ITT requires two conditions: the transferor is ready to transfer the appropriate technology and the transferee has intended to apply it. Lin and Berg (2001) also argue that the level of international experience of both transferors and transferees can have a significant effect on the ITT process. According to Fisher and Ranasinghe (2001), the suitability of the transferor and the cultural identity transferred to working in the partnership should be determined before embarking on the ITT process. This study is mainly based on the transferee's point of view to improve ITT efficiency by identifying potential influencing factors in the acquisition and absorption of the transferred technology.

Cohen and Levinthal (1990) argue that an organization's ability to absorb knowledge is the ability to understand and assimilate new knowledge and apply it to new product development. It includes research and development (R&D) expenditures of an organization (Cohen and Levinthal, 1990; Fosfuri and TRIBO, 2008; Lane et al, 2006; Todorova and Durisin, 2007), the amount equal to Patent (Tsai, 2001), member of the organization in the scientific community (Deeds, 2001), the knowledge management habits of the organization (Jones and Craven, 2000), the team's experienced workforce and business owners (Lim and Klobas, 2000). An organization's ability to absorb knowledge is an important factor affecting the effectiveness of ITT.

Lihua (2001) investigated ITT of the construction industry in three Chinese provinces in the Chinese-foreign joint venture through structural survey. His findings suggest an important link between ITT and economic development, meaning that international technology transfer success will be easily achieved when economic development in a similar transfer recipient country is achieved. assignor. Madu (1989) and Lai and Tsai (2009) continue to support their argument, and they also argue that the size, research and development capacity of the assignee are the main factors influencing the by ITT.

Zhou and Sun (2005) argue that for recipients, there are two main stages where they should pay more attention in the ITT process, including technology acquisition and absorption. Technology acquisition refers to the process of external integration, while absorbing technology involves the internal learning process. Technology acquisition, as a prerequisite for technology absorption, should be given priority consideration. According to the research results of Madu (1989), Lai and Tsai (2009), Odigie (2012) and Megantz (2002), this study argues that governments and technology governance are the two main factors influencing to the acquisition and absorption of technology. Based on the studies of Sun and Scott (2005), Li.Q (2014) also argues that individual learning, group learning, organizational learning and inter-organizational learning are four main factors that influence absorption of technology.

Li.Q (2014) thinks that industry characteristics will also affect the ability to transfer technology, due to the specific characteristics of the industry, requirements for technology transfer will be different, thereby also affecting the ability to transfer technology. Effectiveness in technology transfer in each industry.

When assessing the efficiency of environmental technology transfer, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has divided into four groups of criteria affecting the efficiency of technology transfer, namely: (i) inter-criteria. related to greenhouse gases and the environment; (ii) criteria related to economy and society; (iii) criteria related to administration, institution and politics; and (iv) criteria related to the process.

Rashid Ali Al-Saadi (2010), when studying technology transfer and sustainable growth in Qatar economy, has built an effective technology transfer framework, divided into categories such as: (1) External environment and Government Policy; (2) Technology and external resources; (3) Research and development; (4) The impact of competition on technology transfer; (5) Technology absorption capacity; (6) Value chain and technology transfer; (7) Value network and technology transfer.

Astrid Szogs (2010), while studying technology transfer and capacity building from the perspective of companies in Tanzania, found that factors that influence the success of technology transfer include structural factors. architecture, education and training, transferability, stable government, effective management, transfer targets, research and development (R&D) activities, and the identification and implementation of technologies fit.

Sanjay Kumar et al (2015), when identifying and evaluating factors affecting technology transfer according to systems analysis method (AHP), built up the factors on all 3 factors: input industry, process and

output. In which, the factors are divided into 5 groups: (1) relative economic advantages (higher cost efficiency, higher profit margin, increase in sales); (2) marketing related to profits and resources (Entering new market areas, increasing the usage of existing customers, end-user support, market requirements, competition, evaluation of time); (3) specification (scientific variations, supplier's technological capabilities, technology in accordance with transfer site characteristics, compatibility, functionality, durability, ability to experiment, ability to observe); (4) Legal regulations (authorities, environmental considerations, international organizations); (5) management and strategic issues (strategy, human resources, training and development assistance, manager's commitment).

Each author, when studying technology transfer, looks at a different angle, according to different technology transfer models. Therefore, the view of factors influencing the outcome (or success) of technology transfer is different. In this thesis, the author based on the technology transfer model of Schlie, Radnor, and Wad (1987), and the research results of Li Q. (2014), Kumaraswamy and Shrestha (2002), Malik (2002) to model the factors affecting the efficiency of technology transfer in the security industry sector.

Because the security industry is a specific, relatively new and also confidential field, there has been almost no research on this field, moreover, it is a matter of technology transfer in the industrial sector. security. Therefore, the author chose to study this issue on the basis of many researches on technology transfer and application in specific fields such as security industry. Theoretical basis of factors affecting technology transfer is ranked by the author of the thesis into 6 groups as shown in Table 2.3.

3.2. Factors affecting technology transfer in the security industry

Based on many researches on factors affecting technology transfer, the author of the thesis gives 6 groups of factors that can affect the results of technology transfer in the field of security industry as follows: (i) Characteristics of technology in the security industry; (ii) The external environment (including political, cultural, and social environments); (iii) Government; (iv) The characteristics of the technology transferor; (v) The characteristics of the technology receiver; (vi) Communication environment between the two parties.

Technological characteristics in the security industry are shown through a number of criteria such as: (1) high complexity, requiring a high level of technology that cannot be produced domestically; (2) dual use, can be applied in a variety of fields, including civil and national security; (3) inheritance and in accordance with the current technology of the beneficiary. Transferred technology characteristics must match those of the security industry. The import of appropriate technologies will help to serve the work of the public security forces and thereby also meet the security needs of the people and the whole society. This will promote the creation of demand for technology transfer, contributing to successful transfer activities.

The characteristics of the transferor of the technology will also influence the results of technology transfers in the security industry. These characteristics are demonstrated through: (1) willingness to execute a contract of assignment; (2) has a good cooperative attitude; (3) transfer experience; (4) have the ability to manage and own source technology; (5) has full intellectual property rights in the transferred technology. The assessment of the above criteria will show whether or not the technology transferor is willing to cooperate and has full conditions for cooperation in technology transfer. For a specific field such as the security industry, it is also important to have access to authorized transferors, helping to facilitate the transfer process. More importantly, it can help the technology receiver improve its capacity to innovate, transform and develop technology, and reduce the technology gap with other countries.

The transferee's characteristics include: (1) a willingness to adopt and learn the technology; (2) have a good understanding of the transferor and the technology to be transferred; (3) adequate experience to acquire and apply technology; (4) To invest fully in R&D activities to be able to control technology, improve and perfect technologies; (5) have adequate technical facilities for receiving and operating the technology; (6) Human resources have the necessary skills and qualifications to receive and operate the technology; (7) encourage and create learning environments for employees. The transferee's resources are also crucial to the outcome of technology transfer projects in the security sector. If the resources are insufficient or inadequate with the receiving technology, it will affect the operation of future technologies, causing waste and difficulty in security assurance activities of public security organizations. as well as making the receiver unable to own and

innovate and improve technology, leading to dependence on foreign technology. This is quite dangerous because the autonomy in technology, especially in the security industry, will contribute to ensuring social order and security in the national security.

Government factors have an impact on technology transfer activities in the security industry through activities such as: (1) promulgating policies to encourage enterprises to learn foreign technical know-how; (2) encourage technology receptors to associate with research units and assist enterprises in absorbing technological knowledge; (3) encourage businesses to invest effectively in R&D activities; (4) financial support; (5) protect the interests of enterprises when participating in technology transfer; (6) promulgate clear technical standards for the transferred technology; (7) facilitating the sourcing of technology sources and promoting technology transfer activities; (8) systematic regulation to protect intellectual property rights; (9) regulation of technology transfer processes in the field of security industry; (10) issue a mechanism to form a security industry market in the country; (11) participate in direct supervision in technology transfer project. The factor that the Government is separated from the external environment by the characteristics of the security industry is heavily influenced by the State. Therefore, the author sets aside this factor to assess the impact on technology transfer in the security industry. Since the nature of the security industry is related to safety and security not only of an individual or organization, but also of the country, government regulations have a great influence on technology transfer in the security industry. However, like many other industries, the security industry not only serves the security of the state but also serves civil security needs. Therefore, the control is too tight or too loose, and the lack of necessary government support can also adversely affect the results of technology transfer. In many countries where security industry markets are already established, governments only provide legal and regulatory frameworks in certain special cases, making technology transfer activities simpler. .

In order for technology transfer activities to take place successfully, there is a need to ensure an environment of communication between the two parties: (1) mutual understanding; (2) there is a strong commitment to the performance of our obligations. both sides; (3) have mutual trust; (4) have easy and smooth communication; (5) Parties are willing to support, train and operate transfer technology; (6) there is close supervision of project transfer; (7) can be done through a third party. A favorable environment of contact between the two sides will accelerate technology transfer, help technology quickly be put into production and supply in the market, and reduce intermediate costs and other unnecessary costs.

The external environment (political - social - cultural) can affect through: (1) political stability; (2) cultural differences between the two countries. The peculiarities of the security industry are related to risk. Therefore, factors of the external environment (except for government factors) such as political relations, the cultural and social situation of both host countries and technology transfer countries will also affect the flow, dimensions and methods of technology transfer, thereby affecting the results of technology transfer.

The above six factors are interrelated, creating a unified whole affecting technology transfer activities in the security industry. Because technology transfer is indispensable for prerequisites from the two receiving parties and the technology transfer party. In addition, external environments such as the impact of government policies, the environment of communication between transferors and recipients, the socio-political environment, and the characteristics of technology. There are also complementary effects in different sectors, which may cause the results of technology transfer between the two parties.

4. Evaluation of technology transfer results in the field of security industry

4.1. The concept of technology transfer results

Technology transfer is often repetitive, involves many transfer steps, and is considered successful only if the result is a positive change. The imparting of a new skill or method may not be of real quality when transferring technology, unless and until, there is a change in the outcome (Nishimoto, 1995). Therefore, the challenge here is to emphasize the efficiency of technology transfer, not simply information exchange between the two parties.

Everett M. et al. (2000) define the outcome or efficiency of technology transfer as the degree to which research-based information is successfully transferred from another individual or organization.

Stock and Tatikonda (2000) broaden the concept by assuming that the outcome of technology transfer is defined as the degree to which the use of transfer technology meets the intended functional goals of the technology. delivery companies with defined time and cost goals.

From the perspective of his research, the author said that the results of technology transfer, especially in the security industry, are reflected in the ability of the transferee's ability to meet the defined objectives. socially, economically and economically.

4.2. Criteria for determining the results of technology transfer in the security industry

From constructing the definition of technology transfer results, many studies have given the criteria for technology transfer.

According to Chen (2011), researchers have developed a method to evaluate the outcome of a whole process in which knowledge is passed from the supplier to the receiver. Teece (1976) takes a cost point of view and assumes that the impact of technology transfer can be assessed by the costs involved. Staikarn (1981) considers from an efficiency perspective that the structures of a successful technology transfer include the practical use of the technology, the complete absorption of transfer knowledge, the expansion of the technology into relevant fields, and the ability to change technology as required by specific or objective needs. Mansfield (1982) argues that the success of technology should be comprised of three aspects: the practical use of technology, the achievement of economic efficiency and the ability to develop products. Leonard-Barton & Sinha (1993) applies technology recipient satisfaction to evaluate the efficiency of technology transfer in the electrical industry, factor analysis concludes three structures: efficiency impact. , transparency in the transfer process, the implementation of the goals. Davenport & Prusak (1998) propose that the results of technology transfer must be assessed by the speed of technology transfer, and the depth of technology transfer.

Bhatia (1998) states that the fundamental conclusion about technology transfer is a communicative process. Anyway, the communication conditions between people will facilitate technology transfer. Technology transfer is not just a one-time implementation for all individual processes, but repetitive adjustments that begin with an understanding of business markets, customer opportunities and needs. .

Pursell (2000) shows that technology relevance will influence the transfer of new innovations. Appropriate technology should be cheap, easy to maintain, relevant and compatible with the recipient's creative needs, and easy to learn to use. Appropriate technology is what fits the needs and desires of the individual or receiving group.

According to Rouach (2003), the results of technology transfer can be described as: developing technology in accordance with the strategic needs of the customer, to ensure that the quality and cost of the technology meet the needs of customers, deploy technology in a timely manner, to ensure that the technology is widely used and regularly.

Many researchers believe that the results of technology transfer are expressed in the output value of technology such as the value of the increase in project performance, in terms of economy (Waroonkun & Stewart (2008), and economic achievements, and knowledge growth during implementation (Mohamed et al. (2010)).

From the perspective of research of a specific industry such as security industry, based on the research on the results of technology transfer by many previous researchers, the author of the thesis said that the transfer results technology in the security industry must be measured by indicators of economic value added, added value in the application of production of security industrial products, and increased capacity to absorb knowledge. of the party receiving the technology from the transferred technologies.

In terms of economic indicators, technology transfer results are reflected in the added value that technology brings about in terms of (i) cost relevance and technology quality, (ii) capacity building. competition for security businesses and (iii) respond to the ability to commercialize technology transfer.

In terms of production, technology transfer results are reflected in the added value of production activities, through the criteria of (i) speeding up the time from transfer to when the product is applied. mass production, (ii) increasing the transferee's production capacity, (iii) technology suitable for the Vietnamese environment without the need for further processing: (iv) the product production from transferred technology is modern,

synchronous and suitable to the needs of the industry and the whole society. Production targets also show the quality of technology transferred.

In terms of ability to absorb knowledge and technology transferred in projects, it is necessary to ensure the following criteria: (i) perfecting knowledge and skills for employees; (ii) ensure the confidentiality of security industry operations; (iii) to help the technology receiving party to apply and modify technology features to put into production in the industry in the long term; (iv) help shorten the technology gap in Vietnam's security industry compared to other countries, ensure efficiency in security work in Vietnam.

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